

KEY INDICATORS

With 924,853 hectares, Greece ranked fifth in the EU in 2022. In terms of organic area share, with 17.6%, it was higher than the EU average of 10.6%. Growth from 2001-2022 was more than thirtyfold. Retail sales data from Greece are not provided on a regular basis. Available data show that in 2022, organic retail sales constituted 66 million euros or 0.3% of all retail sales.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2022

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

31,118 ha (0.4%)

924,853 ha (17.6%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2022

2,872%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2022

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

4,248 ha (0.2%)

382,153 ha (21.2%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

18,451 ha (1.6%)

209,981 ha (16.9%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

4,013 ha (0.1%)

332,720 ha (14.8%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

9,898 † (7.6%)

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2022

Producers (Share of Total)

6,680 (0.8%)

58,691 (11.6%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

12

Processors

390

1,727

Importers

4

52

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2022

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

16 M€

66 M€ (0.3%) (2021)

Per Capita Consumption

1.4 €

6.2 € (2021)

Imports

N/D

11,870 †

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN GREECE

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on Eurostat, Greece Ministry of Agriculture, Nic Lampkin

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC RETAIL SALES IN GREECE

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on national data sources. (Updates not available for every year)

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Greek CAP strategic plan gives high importance to organic farming, with 50% of environmental support payments and 11% of total CAP expenditure allocated to conversion under Pillar 2 and maintenance of organic farming under Pillar 1. It foresees a 3.4-fold increase in the supported organic area, from 4.7% in 2018 to 16% of UAA in 2027, but with a reduction in average expenditure per ha despite higher payment rates for some individual crops. The CSP targets an increase in certified organic land to 25% of UAA by 2030. With only 50% of certified organic land supported in 2018, in part due to eligibility and funding restrictions, this may imply a continuation of this situation, or a further substantial increase in supported area later in the decade.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

	2018	2027
Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	248 kha	846 kha (+140%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	4.7 %	16% (+140%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	50%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	97 M€	259 M€ (+167%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	390 €	306 € (-22%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P2)*	1,487 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	2,175 M€	50.4%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	777 M€	
Total CAP Expenditure	13,293 M€	11.2%

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	VINEYARDS	OLIVES
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	211 ^a	72 ^b	550 ^c	850 ^d	669 ^e	629
	2023	P2	232 ^a	216 ^b	848 ^c	951 ^d	856 ^e	692
Change from 2019 to 2023			+10%	+200%	54%	+12%	+28%	+11%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	260 ^a	70 ^b	550 ^c	766 ^d	586 ^e	455
	2023	P1	247 ^a	120 ^b	635 ^c	940 ^d	657 ^e	505
Change from 2019 to 2023			-5%	+71%	+15%	+23%	+12%	+11%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019		-19%	+3%	0	+11%	+14%	+38%
	2023		-6%	+80%	+34%	+1%	+30%	+37%

a) sheep, goats (cows higher); b) cereals (maize higher); c) most vegetables (herbs, tomatoes, aubergines higher); d) stone fruit (citrus lower); e) table grapes higher

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing
- P2 funding use in Madeira. All rates subject to reductions for larger land areas

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Greece has had no previous action plans and is one of very few countries in the EU not yet to have produced or planned an action plan for the current period.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	None	None	None
Current Action Plan	None	None	None

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (NONE)

PRODUCTION

MARKETS

INFORMATION

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (NONE)

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Greece is just over 1%. Organic aquaculture has been supported as part of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture, including investment aids and consumer information. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.